

Histopathological Study of Non-Neoplastic and Neoplastic Ovarian LesionsSnehal Radadiya¹, Pankti Soni², Priyanka Gangani³, Hitesh Rathod⁴^{1,3,4}Junior Resident, Department of Pathology, GMERS Medical College and Hospital, Himmatnagar, Gujarat, India²Senior Resident, Department of Pathology, GMERS Medical College and Hospital, Himmatnagar, Gujarat, India

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Abstract:

Background: The ovary is a vital reproductive organ. It is now believed that most tumors of ovary arise ultimately from one of three ovarian components namely surface epithelium, germ cells and stromal cells, all of these components can give rise to benign and malignant tumors. The aim of the study is to assess the histopathological spectrum of various ovarian lesions and their age wise distribution.

Materials and Methods: The study was carried out at GMERS Medical College and hospital, Himmatnagar in the Department of Pathology, during November 2022 to January 2024. Routine gross examination done and representative sections were taken and stained with hematoxylin and eosin stain for histopathological examination.

Results: Out of 134 cases studied, 102 (77%) were non-neoplastic and remaining 31 (23%) were neoplastic. The most common non-neoplastic lesion found was corpus luteal cysts - 52 cases (51%). Among the 32 neoplastic ovarian lesions, 27 (85%) cases were benign, four (12%) cases were borderline and 1 (3%) case was malignant, serous cystadenoma of the ovary constituted the predominant neoplastic lesion noted. Majority of samples were received from the age group of 30-40 years and were benign and unilateral.

Conclusion: Corpus luteal cyst is the most common ovarian lesion observed in this study and among the ovarian tumors, surface epithelial tumors are commonest followed by germ cell tumors. Majority of cases belonged to age group of 30-40 yrs.

Keywords: Ovarian Neoplasm, Benign lesions, Germ cell tumors.

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Introduction

The ovary plays a pivotal role in reproductive processes, serving as a crucial organ in the generation of offspring. The ovary has three main histologic compartments i.e. the surface Mullerian epithelium, the germ cells and the sexcord stromal cells. Each compartment gives rise to distinct non-neoplastic and neoplastic lesions.[1]

Ovarian cysts are commonly encountered lesions. They are amongst the most frequent cause of hospitalization and surgery in gynaecologic practice. One cannot confidently distinguish a benign lesion from a malignant one on the basis of clinical, radiological or gross characteristics alone so a histopathology examination is a must as it guides therapy.[2]

Ovarian neoplasms captivate our interest due to their intricate histogenesis, clinical patterns, and potential for malignancy in women. Ranking as the third most prevalent primary malignancy in the female genital tract, after cervix and endometrium, the ovary contributes to 30% of all cancers in this

tract. These tumors exhibit diverse behaviour, often eluding detection until they reach a substantial size. The challenge lies in their vague symptoms or asymptomatic nature, leading to a gradual manifestation over time without a defined screening program. Accurate diagnosis of various histological patterns is crucial for effective treatment and prognosis.[3] Ovarian carcinoma is a significant contributor to female cancer-related deaths and ranks as the fifth leading cause of cancer fatalities in women. Ovarian tumors make up approximately 30% of all female genital tract cancers, with higher incidence rates in economically advanced countries. Surface epithelial-stromal carcinomas constitute 90% of ovarian cancers. Notably, factors like high parity and oral contraceptive use are linked to a decreased risk of developing these surface-origin carcinomas [4]

Materials and Method

The study was carried out at GMERS Medical College and hospital, Himmatnagar in the Department of Pathology, during November 2022 to January 2024. In this prospective study, an examination of ovarian lesions was conducted. Oophorectomy specimens were consecutively received in 10% formalin from the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, accompanied by a requisition form containing pertinent clinical features, age, radiological findings, and provisional diagnosis. Upon receipt, the ovarian specimens were weighed, and comprehensive gross photographs of both the external and cut surfaces were captured. The representative tissue sections were taken and tissues were processed by routine paraffin techniques and sections stained with Haematoxylin and Eosin were taken for microscopic examination.

Subsequently, non-neoplastic and neoplastic lesions from representative sections were meticulously examined and classified in accordance with the World Health Organisation (WHO) classification of 2020. [5].

Result

In the present study, total 262 ovarian specimens were received. Out of 262 specimens, 128 showed no specific pathology, other than normal findings. Hence, only 134 cases were included in the present study.

Amongst 134 cases studied during study period, 102 were non-neoplastic and remaining 32 were neoplastic. The most common non-neoplastic lesion found was corpus luteal cysts 52 cases followed by solitary follicular cysts 44 cases, with 1 case of haemorrhagic follicular cyst and 5 cases of haemorrhagic corpus luteal cyst. (Table 1)

Table 1: Frequency of Non-neoplastic lesions of ovary

Non-neoplastic lesions of ovary	Number of cases	Percentage
Follicular cyst	44	43%
Corpus luteal cyst	52	51%
Hemorrhagic follicular cyst	01	01%
Hemorrhagic corpus luteal cyst	05	05%
Total	102	100%

Among the 32 neoplastic ovarian lesions, 27 cases were benign, 4 cases were at borderline and 1 case was malignant. (Table-2)

In 27 benign ovarian neoplasm, most common seen lesion was serous cystadenoma with 13 cases with 4 cases shows bilateral ovarian involvement followed by mucinous cystadenoma with 9 cases, 4

cases of mature cystic teratoma and 1 case of Brenner tumor.

Among the 4 borderline ovarian lesion 2 cases were borderline mucinous tumor, 1 case was borderline papillary serous tumor, 1 case was borderline seromucinous tumor, and in malignant ovarian lesion, 1 case was of granulosa cell tumour.

Table 2: Frequency of Neoplastic lesions of ovary

Neoplastic lesions of ovary	Number of cases	Percentage (%)
Benign	27	85
Borderline	04	12
Malignant	01	03
Total	32	100

These Neoplastic lesions were classified according to WHO classification and categorized into 4 main groups. (Table-3)

Table 3: Frequency of neoplastic lesions of ovary according to WHO classification

Type of Tumor	Number of cases (%)		
	Benign	Borderline	Malignant
(1) Surface epithelial tumors			
• Serous tumors	13	01	00
• Mucinous tumors	10	02	00
• Endometrioid tumors	00	00	00
• Transitional cell tumors	01	00	00
(2) Sex cord stromal tumors			
• Granulosa cell tumors	01		
• Fibroma	00		
• Thecoma	00		

(3) Germ cell tumors	
• Mature teratoma	04
• Immature teratoma	00
• Dysgerminoma	00
• Yolk sac tumor	00

Figure 1: Gross specimen of follicular cyst showing solitary, thin walled cyst containing clear fluid

Figure 2: Gross specimen of hemorrhagic corpus luteal cyst

Figure 3: Gross specimen of granulosa cell tumor showing large, soft fleshy tumor with cream color appearance

Figure 4: Granulosa cell tumor with tumor cell arranged in sheets with few foci of call-exner bodies, few of nuclei have a groove (H&E 10x)

Figure 5: Benign Brenner's tumor shows islands of transitional epithelium; cells have abundant cytoplasm (H&E 40x)

Figure 6: Serous borderline tumor showing fibrous papillary fronds progressively branching into small cores (H&E 10x)

Figure 7: Mature cystic teratoma showing thyroid follicles (H&E 10x)

Most of the benign tumour were observed in the age group of 31-40 years, and most of the malignant tumours cases were common in elderly (>40 years) age group. In our study, comprised of 32 cases of neoplastic lesions of ovary, in which 12 patients had bilateral ovarian tumours, while majority were unilateral. Right-sided lesions were more common than Left side. On gross examination 40%, cases were cystic, 30% were solid and 30% cases were partly solid and partly cystic.

Discussion

Ovarian cancer is the second leading cause of mortality among all gynecological cancers. Due to similar clinical presentations, there is confusion in the diagnosis of non-neoplastic and neoplastic lesions of ovary although it is diagnosed as a mass or cystic lesion on ultrasonography and hence removed prophylactically. Ovarian tumour may occur at any age, including infancy and childhood. Incidence rate, however increase with age, with the greatest number of new cases being diagnosed beyond 4th decade. [6].

In clinically suspected ovarian pathology cases, the most common clinical symptoms were abdominal pain, menstrual irregularities or abnormal vaginal bleeding and mass per abdomen.

In present study, 132 ovarian lesions of non-neoplastic and neoplastic origins were evaluated to find out incidence, clinical and histopathological features. The non-neoplastic lesions like follicular or corpus luteum cysts are the commonly encountered conditions. In present study cystic lesion like follicular cyst 44 cases (43%), corpus luteum cyst 52 cases (51%) and hemorrhagic cyst 6 cases (06%) were noted. Incidence of this study is in accordance with studies conducted by Gaikwad S.L. et al which shows 27.7% of corpus luteum cyst followed by 21.8% of follicular cyst [7]. In the

present study, 32 neoplastic lesions were diagnosed most common was benign followed by, borderline malignancy and malignant tumour. Incidence of surface epithelial tumours were commonest (84%) followed by germ cell tumours (13%), sex cord (3%). Similar observations were seen in study done by Kanthikar SN et al [8].

In present study, on gross examination majority of benign tumours were cystic as compared to malignant, which were solid in consistency followed by partly cystic and partly solid. Ovarian cancers sometimes may remain subtle until the advanced stage [9]. However, histomorphological study of tumour is still a gold standard method.

Conclusion

Ovarian lesion manifests a complex wide spectrum. Number of various clinical parameters such as age of the patient, presenting complaints, location of lump and histomorphological parameters and advanced newer diagnostic modalities like immunohistochemistry, morphometric analysis can help to diagnose and to decide treatment plan.

Because of the geographic location, poverty and illiteracy, patients seek medical advice late in rural health facility. Therefore, awareness among public and doctors, educating people, passive surveillance, and community screening facility will be helpful in early detection of the ovarian lesions and tumours.

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